

Grammatical issues in learning language

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Annotation: In this article, the problems that arise in language learning and their solutions are discussed in detail.

Keywords: Learning foreign languages, grammar, grammatical skills.

Learning foreign languages comprise several aspects. One such aspect is grammar. Perhaps, not a single aspect of language teaching has been the subject of such intensive discussions and discussions as grammar for many years. Grammar occupies an important place in teaching foreign language speaking; it is a kind of framework on which vocabulary is based. Learning grammar and the correct design of the utterance, as well as recognition of grammatical forms in speech and writing, occurs through the formation of grammatical skills.

It is impossible to take the grammar from speech, without a grammar mastery of any form of speech is not imagined, since the grammar, along with the vocabulary and sound composition, is the material basis of speech. Grammar has an organizing role.

You need to keep in mind the following significant differences in the conditions of mastering the native and foreign language, which affect the approach to teaching grammar of a foreign language:

-The native language is the primary vital means of communication. It is absorbed in childhood in parallel with the adaptation of the child to the environment.

-A foreign language is a secondary means of communication, the use of which is not dictated by vital necessity; mastering a foreign language begins at school age, when the main means of communication, the native language, has already developed; therefore, special efforts are required to motivate learning the language.

-The native language is mastered in a natural and abundant linguistic environment, from which the child, without special efforts, that is, involuntarily and in a short time, isolates patterns.

-Mastering a foreign language takes place in a learning environment in a foreign environment for the student. There is no sufficient basis for the involuntary identification of patterns. Therefore, when mastering grammar in a school course of a foreign language, special attention should be paid to theory and its optimal combination with speech practice, as well as to the ratio of an arbitrary form of attention to involuntary, i.e., the consistent implementation of the principle of consciousness.

The principle of consciousness underlies all methods used in mastering grammar each method establishes its own correlation between theory and practice. It is only important to keep in mind the following: the application of a "pure" theory without its confirmation by the concrete facts of the functioning of the grammatical phenomenon, just as "pure" practice without its understanding are not acceptable when mastering grammar in a school course of a foreign language.

To solve the problems of teaching a grammar of a foreign language, it is necessary to clarify the concept of "grammar", to establish the relationship of the grammar of a foreign language with specific features with the practice of teaching, pedagogy, psychology, linguistics and consider its pedagogical goals.

The communicative goal of grammar education in high school allows us to formulate the basic requirement for grammatical material to be learned in high school: it must be sufficient for using the language as a means of communication within the limits set by the program and real for learning it in these conditions. If we keep in mind that the creation of grammatical skills is associated with the expenditure of a significant amount of time for performing exercises, then it is unlikely to master all the phenomena of a foreign language to the degree of automated use of them in school learning a foreign language. Certain, very significant restrictions are needed in the selection of grammatical material and, above all, those grammatical phenomena that students

should be proficient in - in productive and receptive types of speech activity. The overestimation of the volume of actively assimilated grammatical material, as practice shows, negatively affects the quality of possession: students do not have enough firm knowledge of the most elementary phenomena of morphology and syntax. Therefore, it is possible and advisable to limit the amount of material, in particular grammar, taking into account the specific conditions for teaching a foreign language.

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